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Impact Of Politics On States Compliance With The Decisions Of The ICJ

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ABSTRACT

The International Court of Justice (ICJ) replaced the Permanent Court of International Justice (PCIJ) as the judicial arm of the United Nations Organization.¹ The Court sits in the Hague, the Netherlands. All member states of the United Nations are ipso facto parties to the Statute of the ICJ.² Some scholars have argued that compliance with ICJ decisions has been largely ineffective as a result of the faulty structure of the court's jurisdiction. Some other scholars hold the view that the court has been largely successful as an arbiter. It is argued in this work the level of compliance with the decisions of the ICJ has been largely satisfactory and that the ICJ not being the enforcement arm of the United Nations Organization has done well in its function of adjudication of disputes between states and rendering of advisory opinion on legal questions to the organs of the United Nations.

Keywords: Politics, Compliance, States, International Court of Justice, Impact.

INTRODUCTION

The primary function of the ICJ is the adjudication of disputes between States and rendering of advisory opinion on any legal question to the organs of the United Nations.³ A non member state of the United Nations may become a party to a dispute before the ICJ upon fulfilling conditions that may be determined by the General Assembly.⁴ The Court functions in accordance with its statute which forms an integral part of the United Nations Charter.⁵ The ICJ may assume jurisdiction in three ways; by special agreement, by treaty and by unilateral declaration under the optional clause. In some cases, jurisdiction may be based on more than one source.⁶

The Cases that come before the ICJ for adjudication are often linked with political factors. For example, some cases may be the subject of consideration before any of the political organs of the UN or may be the subject of bilateral negotiations between the parties.⁷

The political nature of disputes involving states makes states fairly reluctant to adopt adjudication as the best possible means of settling their disputes. This has implications on the number of cases that come before the ICJ. In order to avoid legal defeat, some states refuse to submit to the jurisdiction of the court or they may decline to appear or comply with its decision if the court assumes jurisdiction.⁸

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¹ UN Charter Article 92

² Ibid Article 93

³ Ibid Article 96

⁴ Ibid Article 93 (2)

⁵ Ibid Article 92

⁶ Eric Posner; "The Decline of the International Court of Justice" (John M. Olin Program in Law and Economics Working Paper No. 233, 2004) <http://www.Law.Uchicago.edu/lawecon/index.html> accessed 22nd May 2026.

⁷ MN Shaw, International Law (7th edn, Cambridge University Press 2014) 771

⁸ JK Patrick, "The International Court of Justice: Crisis and Reformation" (1987) 12 Yale Journal of International Law 342

The Court has noted that its major preoccupation is to state the law and decide cases on the basis of International Law. In *Nicaragua v Honduras*,⁹ the ICJ noted that a political dispute may be brought before the court. The Court tries to establish that the dispute in question is a legal dispute and determines if the dispute is one that is capable of being resolved by applying the principles of international law.

It would appear that states appearing before the ICJ do not always agree with the courts understanding and application of the principles of International law. The disagreement on applicable principles appears to make some states reluctant to submit their disputes to the Court for adjudication.¹⁰

In accepting or declining jurisdiction, the Court considers three main criteria. The first is consistency with principles in previous cases to provide some level of predictability. Secondly, the court considers certitude wherein the court determines the ground most secure in law. Finally, the court considers the political implications and consequences on pending cases.¹¹

Beyond seeking to separate purely political disputes from legal disputes, the court also determines the very important issue of jurisdiction. This work focus mainly on the compulsory jurisdiction of the ICJ under the optional clause since it is the major way by which states invoke the jurisdiction of the Court, a declaration of compulsory jurisdiction, by which they confer jurisdiction to the ICJ in advance of any dispute.

Contentious jurisdiction is not without its limitations. Firstly, the principle of reciprocity requires that both parties to any dispute must accept the same obligations. Secondly, states qualify their declarations by inserting reservation which generally limits or narrows their obligations contained in the declaration by which they submit themselves to the Courts jurisdiction.¹²

There appears to be some unrealistic expectations from the Court. It is also argued that the work of the court can be better appreciated if the court is unburdened of such unrealistic expectations, which is what this work seeks to do. This work examined the historical development of the ICJ in order to show that from its inception, political consideration influenced the formation of the court as well as its jurisdiction especially the optional clause. In respect of compliance by State parties this study evaluated some factors that affect compliance. The pattern of compliance before and after the landmark *Nicaragua v US*¹³ judgement will be examined to show a growing trend towards full or partial compliance.

This work will discuss political factors that affect compliance with the judgment of the ICJ. In this regard, the activities of States that affect compliance will be the focus. An evaluation of some of the cases that have been decided by the Court after 1987, when the Court gave its decision in the case of *United States of America v. Nicaragua*. Phillip Couvreur a former ICJ registrar observed that compliance is sometimes hard to determine because judgements take different forms; it may take the form of declarations which may not reflect actual conduct and the effect may only become apparent long after the judgment is given. The legal or political situation may witness some change after the judgment.¹⁴

Political Constrains of the ICJ

H. Lauterpacht in his work on the ICJ observed that the more sensitive the case is from a political perspective, the more the respondent will be inclined to resist the relevant clause on which the applicant relies as a ground for compulsory jurisdiction.¹⁵ Scholars have opined that anything less than a clear

⁹ The Armed Actions (*Nicaragua v Honduras*) case, ICJ Reports, 1988, pp.16,19

¹⁰ Shaw 771

¹¹ *Serbia and Montenegro v UK* ICJ 2004 p. 1307, 1353-4

¹² Patrick (n 8) 342

¹³ *Military and Paramilitary Activities in and against Nicaragua* (Supra)

¹⁴ Philip Couvreur, "The Effectiveness of the International Court of Justice in the peaceful settlements of international disputes", in *INTERNATIONAL COURT OF JUSTICE: ITS FUTURE ROLE AFTER FIFTY YEARS* 83, 112 (A.S Muller et al. eds 1997).

¹⁵ H. Lauterpacht, "The Development of International Law by the International Court (1958) London: Stevens & Sons.; New York: Federick A. Praeger pp. xx, 408. Index. (reprinted in 1982).

indication of consent by a state party in a given case is likely to run non-compliance risk.¹⁶ It is important however to observe that once the ICJ has rendered a judgment, the legal dispute before the Court is considered settled and the Court no longer has jurisdiction. The ICJ does not monitor compliance or takes steps towards ensuring compliance. Once a case is removed from its docket, it does not receive information from the parties in any way and it is not always possible to discern the responses of the parties from public sources.¹⁷

In respect of compliance perhaps the most notable case of open defiance with the judgment of the ICJ remains the *Nicaragua v. United States of America* dispute.¹⁸ The contentious nature of the Court's assertion of jurisdiction, coupled with the non-appearance of the United States at the merit phase and its subsequent defiance of that judgment marked a paradigm shift as the last in the series of instances of open defiance and non-appearance.¹⁹ Until recently where the court stated that orders on provisional measures had binding effect, states had argued with respect to the provisions of Article 41 of the ICJ statute that judgment of the ICJ did not have a binding effect on them.

Influence of International Politics on the Historical Evolution of the ICJ

After the Second World War, strong sentiment favored the establishment of a new International Court as part of the United Nations. When the four sponsoring powers, the United States, the United Kingdom, the Soviet Union and the Republic of China, developed the Dumbarton Oaks Proposals for the United Nations,²⁰ they proposed that an International Court be created as the principal judicial organ of the United Nations and that all members of the United Nations be parties to the Statute of the Court.²¹

The United Nations Conference on International Organization convened in San Francisco USA on April 25, 1945, to consider and approve the charters of the UN and the court. In preparation for the San Francisco Conference, the Committee of Jurists developed two variations of compulsory jurisdiction. One retained the optional clause, while the other gave the court compulsory jurisdiction over all legal disputes.²²

At the conference, the majority of States again favored automatic compulsory Jurisdiction.²³ Both the United States of America and the Soviet Union, however, were unalterably opposed,²⁴ and the United Kingdom shared their view.²⁵ Such forceful opposition to compulsory jurisdiction at this critical juncture resulted in retention of the optional clause.²⁶

The optional clause system imposed two major limitations on jurisdiction. First, the principle of reciprocity required that consent to jurisdiction be granted only "in relation to any other member or State accepting the same obligation,"²⁷ These words were inserted to limit a state's exposure to "cases when the dispute fails

¹⁶ Andrew Coleman; "The International Court of Justice and Highly Political Matters" *Melbourne Journal of International Law*, (2003) Vol. 4 No 1

¹⁷ Joan Donoghue: *Supra* at pp, 117

¹⁸ *Military and Paramilitary Activities in and against Nicaragua (Nicaragua v. US)*, Provisional measures (1984) ICP Rep. 169; Jurisdiction and Admissibility (1984) ICJ Rep 392; Merits (1986) ICJ Rep 14.

¹⁹ C. Schulte, *Compliance with Decisions of the International Court of Justice* (2004) 403

²⁰ Doc. IG/I, 3 U.N.C.I.O. Docs 1, 25 (1945)

²¹ *Ibid* 11-12

²² Waldock 244-45 (citing 14 U.N.C.I.O 667-68)

²³ US. DEPT OF STATE, PUB. NO. 2491. INTERNATIONAL COURT OF JUSTICE: SELECTED DOCUMENTS RELATING TO DRAFTING OF THE STATUTE 33-45 (1946)

²⁴ Summary Report of the Fourteenth Meeting of Committee IV, I, Doc. 661, IV/1/50, 13 U.N.C.I.O. Docs. 226 (1945)

²⁵ *Ibid.* at 227; see also US DEPT OF STATE, I FOREIGN RELATIONS OF THE UNITED STATES 962 (1945) (statement of H. Green Hackworth, Legal Adviser to the Department of state).

²⁶ Waldock 245

²⁷ ICJ Statute, Art. 36(2); see also Waldock 255 (explaining that language "on condition of reciprocity on part of several or certain states" was added in order to meet the concern of the Brazilian Committee of Jurists that Brazil should not accept compulsory jurisdiction until at least some of the great powers also accepted jurisdiction)

within a category of disputes covered by both their declarations.”²⁸ As a result, a State is not bound beyond the scope of its consent or that of the opposing State.²⁹

The second major limitation permitted States to qualify their declaration by attaching reservations limiting the scope of the obligation assumed by the declaration. Although, the Statute of the Court does not specifically confer a general power of reservation, the First Committee of the Fourth Commission, in proposing the Statute, considered the attachment of reservations to be an established right of States under permanent court and found any specific mention of them unnecessary.³⁰ In the US, the Harry Truman Administration supported a US declaration accepting the court's compulsory jurisdiction.³¹ The US Senate however, passed a resolution on the issue of the Court's compulsory jurisdiction containing three reservations: one covering disputes involving matters essentially within the domestic jurisdiction of the United States, as determined by the United States (the Connally Reservation);³² one covering disputes entrusted to other tribunals by agreement; and one covering disputes arising under a multilateral treaty unless all parties are present or the United States specifically agrees to jurisdiction.³³ The formation of the ICJ and the jurisdiction it eventually obtained was thus, largely a product of politics. International politics has from formation played a role in the success or otherwise of the ICJ.

From the foregoing, it is clear that political factors and political compromise shaped even the kind of jurisdiction that the ICJ eventually got. In the opinion of Tom Ginsburg³⁴ one way to characterize political constraints is to focus on the points in time at such constraints are executed. It will be useful to distinguish between *ex ante* and *ex post* constraints. *Ex ante* constraints are implemented before decisions are made and include the definition of jurisdiction; formal appointment mechanisms that shape the court; and discursive techniques to get judges to internalize state values. *Ex post* constraints, on the other hand are exercised after the judges render a decision, and include efforts to ignore, overrule, or reject decisions. An initial point at which political constraints become apparent is institutional design, The instruments that establish and regulate tribunals provide opportunities for states to tinker with institutional design in ways that ensure responsiveness to political interests, both *ex ante* and *ex post*.

The political constraints on the ICJ take the form of both *Ex ante* and *Ex post* constraints because, political influence on the Court as earlier pointed out began with the definition of its jurisdiction as captured in Article 36 of the statute of the Court up to appointment mechanisms and eventually the decision by State parties on whether to comply to ICJ decision or to ignore it. Even in respect of pressure from the international community highlighted in this work as a means of ensuring compliance or a decision to be taken by the Security Council of the UN to enforce a particular judgement referred to it, political considerations will play out. For example, where a permanent member of the Security Council is the defaulting party, it will be difficult if not almost impossible to compel the party to comply with the decision of the ICJ, because of the effect of a veto vote at the Security Council. This effect goes beyond

²⁸ Waldock 256 (emphasis deleted)

²⁹ Anglo - Iranian Oil CO. (*UK v. Iran*). 1952 AICJ 93; 103 (preliminary Objection of July 22)

³⁰ Report of the Rapporteur of Committee IV/I. Doc. 913, IV, 13 U.N C.I.O. Docs. 391-92 (1945)

³¹ Compulsory Jurisdiction, International Court of Justice: Hearings on S. Res. 196 Before a Subcomm. of the Senate Comm. on Foreign Relation, 79th cong., 2d Sss. 14-15 (1946) letters of President Truman and Secretary of States Byrnes [hereinafter 1946 Hearings]: see Iso id at 133 (statement Under Secretary of State Dean Acheson)

³² Senator Conally of Texas introduced this amendment, which would allow the United States to determine for itself what question fell within its domestic jurisdiction, during the Senate floor debates. see 92 CONG. REC. SIO, 621 (1946). The amendment was vigorously opposed by Senator Morse and Senator Thomas Chairman of the Senate sub-committee responsible for writing the report. Id, at S10, 625-26, Thomas argued that the self-judging reservation was inconsistent with the court's authority to determine its own jurisdiction. granted in article 36(6) Of its statute, Id, at SIO,625-26 (1946), noted legal scholars have shared this assessment. see, eg. Compulsory jurisdiction, International Court of Justice: Hearings on S. Res. 94 before the Comm. on Foreign Relations, 86th cong., 2d Sess. 190 -203 Harvard Law School held the opinion that the Conally Reservation conflicted with the ICJ Statute) [hereinafter 1960 Hearings].

³³ 92 CONG. REC. S10, 706 (1946). see US Declaration, supra note 2

³⁴ Tom Ginsburg, "Political Constraints on International Courts" (University of Chicago Public Law & Legal Theory Working Paper No. 453, 2013)

just the decisions of the ICJ. It manifests even in resolutions taken by the General Assembly or the Security Council.

Compliance with the Judgment of the ICJ

To be meaningful compliance should consist of acceptance of the judgment as final and reasonable performance in good faith of any binding obligation.³⁵ In this context it should be clear that the judgment is a clear and unambiguous final pronouncement of the Court.

Good faith in turn has been defined by the ICJ in one context as a duty to give effect to the judgment of the court. The overriding formation of the judicial powers of enforcements is to provide for the judgment creditor the fruits of the judgment, to obtain for him due satisfaction, compensation, restitution, performance or compliance with what the court has granted by way of remedy or relief.³⁶ Defiance on the other hand, involves whole sale rejection of the judgment as invalid coupled with a refusal to comply.³⁷

While examining the compliance record of ICJ judgments from 1946-2003 Schulte concluded that of the 27 distinct cases that reached a judgment on the merits a generally satisfactory compliance record for judgment was achieved.³⁸ Jonathan Charney conducted an empirical study of State compliance with final decisions in 1987 in the wake of Military and Paramilitary Activities in and Against Nicaragua when the United States withdrew from the Court's compulsory jurisdiction. He found that ICJ decisions (especially final judgments) were generally accorded a large amount of deference. Cases with contemporaneous consent or submitted by special agreements received a high degree of compliance³⁹

Why States Comply

Several reasons have been advanced for why states comply with the Judgement of the ICJ. In this work, an analysis shall be made of reasons which include external political pressure from the international community, desire to maintain national reputation, nature of the judgement and international political influence.⁴⁰

Pressure from the international community plays an important role towards ensuring compliance with judgements of the ICJ. The desire of States to retain their membership of international organizations and to continue to receive benefits that flow from such membership puts States under pressure to comply with the judgement of the ICJ. For example, following Nigeria's disapproval of the Court's judgement in the land and maritime boundary dispute between Nigeria and Cameroon - the US, France, and the UK put substantial pressure on Nigeria to comply with the judgement.⁴¹ This eventually led to full compliance with the judgement by Nigeria.

International organizations play a role in ensuring compliance with judgements of the ICJ. Since nearly all nations of the world belong to the United Nations, there is an obligation to the above by Article 94(1) of the UN Charter which provides thus: "Each member of the United Nations undertakes to comply with the decision of the International Court of Justice in any case to which it is a party." The obligation to comply with the ICJ judgement by member states who are parties to the judgement is further reinforced by Article 94(2): "If any party to a case fails to perform the obligations incumbent upon it under a judgement rendered by the Court, the other party may have recourse to the Security Council which may, if it deems necessary, make recommendations or decide upon measures to be taken to give effect to the judgement."

³⁵ A Chayes and AH Chayes, *The New Sovereignty: Compliance with International Regulatory Agreement* (1995) PP 17-22

³⁶ Afe Babalola: *Enforcement of Judgments* (Intec Printers 2003)

³⁷ Liamzon.

³⁸ Schulte 403

³⁹ Colter Paulson: "Compliance with Final Judgments of the International Court of Justice Since 1987" *The American Journal of International Law*. Cambridge University Press (2004), Vol. 98, No. 3 (Jul., 2004) pp. 434-461

⁴⁰ Heather I. Jones, "Why Comply? An Analysis of Trends in Compliance with Judgement of the International Court of Justice since Nicaragua, (2012) 12 *Chicago Kart journal of International and Comparative Law* 60

⁴¹ AP Lianzon, "*Jurisdiction and Compliance in Recent Decisions of the ICJ*" 18 *Eur. Journal of International Law*, 815, 836.

The dispute involving Belgium and the Congo⁴² and the compliance with the decision reached by the ICJ shows the extent to which pressure from international organizations can lead to compliance. The decision of the ICJ made Belgium to withdraw the arrest warrant issued against the foreign minister of the Democratic Republic of Congo. Belgium made changes to its law on universal jurisdiction to bring it in compliance with its obligations under Article 94(1) of the UN Charter, Non-compliance with judgements of the ICJ could come with severe reputation damage to the state.

A second reason for compliance with ICJ judgement and indeed with international law is the presence of shared interests by states towards achieving a solution to disputes that may arise between or among State parties. Parties may have a common interest towards preventing an escalation of any dispute especially where close ties exist between the States. The nature of the judgement given by the ICJ is of importance in determining the ease with which states comply. Generally, judgements that entail compromise or allow for co-operative efforts are easier for States to comply with.⁴³

Internal political pressure is a third reason why states comply with judgements of the ICJ. Internal political pressure could be put on the State party either to defy or comply with the judgements of the ICJ. As highlighted earlier, the nature of the judgement could lead to the kind of pressure that the state will face towards complying or defying the judgement.

Analysis of States Compliance with Judgments of the ICJ Post Nicaragua v. US

Land, Island and Maritime Frontier Dispute (El Salvador v Honduras; Nicaragua Intervening).

Facts: A boundary dispute between El Salvador and Honduras dating back to the 19th century involving six pockets of land totaling 4405sq. km and a maritime boundary encompassing three islands.⁴⁴ Large scale conflict was averted, however through the organization of American State (OAS) intervention which resulted in a 1980 Peace Treaty.⁴⁵ With the OAS assistance in the negotiations Honduras and El Salvador submitted the dispute, by special agreement to a Chamber of the ICJ.⁴⁶ The court handed down final judgment in 1992 resulting in 2/3 of the disputed area (about 300 sq. km) being held to belong to Honduras and 140 sq. km given to El Salvador.

Post Judgement: both states announced a willingness to accept the ICJ judgment. El Salvador expressed concern for the rights of its citizen living within the disputed area.

An agreement was reached in 1998 providing for the rights of the resident within the border area who had a right to choose their nationality and guaranteed acquired rights regardless of the choice made. Despite the agreement reached minor Skirmishers still occurred. Allegations of non-compliance with the ICJ judgment was made by Honduras against El Salvador resulting in a formal letter to the UN Secretary General and subsequently a formal complaint of non-compliance under Article 94 (2) of the UN Charter.

In October 2002, El Salvador responded to the accusation by the Honduras by denying the accusation and also requested a review of the ICJ judgment. The application by El Salvador was rejected. Eventually, by agreement of all the parties, demarcation of the affected land and maritime boundary began and this considerably reduced the likelihood of any large-scale conflict. The judgment has evidently fostered so much confidence in the region that Honduras professed its pleasure at Nicaragua taking their border dispute, to the ICJ, saying it now views the ICJ as an honorable alternative to methods that have placed regional security and integrations at risk.

⁴² ICJ Report 2002 pg. 1

⁴³ Jones (n 24) 72

⁴⁴ Paulso 437 citing President of El Salvador on ICJ Ruling on border dispute, BBC Summary of World Broadcast, 4 September 1992 (LEXIS, News Library. All news file)

⁴⁵ General Peace Treaty, El Salvador-Honduras, 30 October 1980, 1310 UNTS 213

⁴⁶ Merrills, "The International Court of Justice and The Adjudication of Territorial and Boundary Disputes" (2000) 13 *Leiden J Intl 876*

Territorial Dispute (Libya/Chad)

Facts: The Case involved a territorial dispute between Libya and Chad over a region covering 330,000 sq. km Aouzon strip, a recourse rich area occupied by Libya in 1973. War broke out between the 2 countries between 1986-1987. At the cessation of hostilities both parties sought peace in 1989.

Assumption of jurisdiction by the ICJ: both States agreed to submit the dispute to the ICJ for settlement with the diplomatic effort of the Organization of African Unity (OAU). Libya notified the ICJ on 31st August while Chad notified the ICJ on 3rd September, 1989.⁴⁷

Judgment: the ICJ handed down judgment in February 1994, awarding the entire Aouzon strip to Chad.⁴⁸

Post Judgment/Compliance: Libya initially rejected the ICJ judgment which was clearly against her. However, Libya subsequently yielded and agreed to comply with the terms of the judgment after months of negotiations. The ICJ judgment ended the Libyan occupation of the Aouzon strip.⁴⁹

Despite the agreement by Libya to fully comply with the judgment of the ICJ, reports however indicate that it maintained some presence in the Aouzon strip either by presence of its nationals within the strip or through its support for rebels fighting the Chadian Government from within the Aouzon strip. It is doubtful if Libya indeed terminated its occupation of the Aouzon strip.⁵⁰

Despite the challenges with full compliance with the ICJ judgment by Libya. It is important to note that the judgment contributed significantly toward the resolution of the boundary dispute and resultant skirmishes and all-out war.

Gabcikoro-Nagymaros Project (Hungary/Slovakia)

By an agreement reached between Hungary and the then Republic of Czechoslovakia Republics (now Slovakia and Czech Republics) both countries agree to construct the Nagymaros Project which involved building of dams along the Dan Ube River. While Czechoslovakia proceeded with its obligation under the agreement, it appeared that Hungary abandoned the project owing to fear of damaging the Budapest water project.⁵¹

Assumption of jurisdiction by the ICJ: By agreement, Hungary and Slovakia submitted the dispute to the ICJ in 1993.⁵²

Judgment: In 1997, the ICJ entered judgment upholding Slovakia's agreement that the 1977 treaty remained valid irrespective of the argument advanced by Hungary expressing fear of environmental consequences as its reason for failing to continue with the project. The Court ordered the parties to work out an amicable arrangement towards giving effect to the judgment of the Court.⁵³

Compliance: in line with the judgment of the ICJ both countries entered into negotiations as to how to comply or give effect to the judgment. Negotiation broke down severally and Slovakia had courage to go back and forth from the ICJ seeking further orders to compel Hungary to comply, Assessing compliance in Gabcikoro Nagymaros is difficult because of the Court's requirement for further negotiations, which did little to resolve the underlying dispute and left the parties arguably in the same position they were before the case.⁵⁴

⁴⁷ See Framework Agreement on the Peaceful Settlement of the Territorial Dispute. 31 Aug. 1989 1545 UNTS 101,

⁴⁸ Ajibola, "Compliance with Judgment of the International Court of Justice" in M Butlerman and M Kuijter (eds). *Compliance with Judgment of International Court* (1996) 17.

⁴⁹ U.S Department of State, State Department Background, Note on Chad: Sept. 2006

⁵⁰ Paulson 441

⁵¹ (1997) ICJ Rep. 1 Paras 15-22, 371ML (1993) 162.

⁵² Special agreement for submission to the ICJ differences between them concerning the Gabeikoro Nagymaros Project (Hungary/Slovakia): 7 April 1993, 32 ILM (1993) 1293.

⁵³ Ibid at paras. 144-145.

⁵⁴ Liamzou

Land and Maritime Boundary Dispute between Cameroon and Nigeria (Cameroon v Nigeria; Equatorial Guinea Intervening)

Fact: Cameroon and Nigeria are states situated on the West Coast of Africa. Their land boundaries extend from Lake Chad in the north to the Bakassi Peninsula in the south. Sovereignty over the Bakassi Peninsula and parts of the Lake Chad region had been a subject of long dispute between the 2 states. The dispute between the parties as regards their boundary falls within an historical framework marked initially in the 19th and early 20th centuries by the action of the European powers. The delimitation of the parties' maritime boundary is an issue of more recent origin, the history of which likewise involves various international instruments.⁵⁵

Assumption of jurisdiction by the ICJ: On 29th March 1994, Cameroon initiated proceedings by an application inviting the Court to determine the course of the maritime boundary between the 2 States beyond the line fixed in 1975. Both parties made declaration accepting the jurisdiction of the Court.

On 30th June 1999, Equatorial Guinea filed an application for permission to intervene in the dispute pursuant to Article 62 of the statute of the ICJ. Neither Cameroon nor Nigeria objected to Equatorial Guinea intervening.

Judgment: On 10th October 2002, the ICJ entered judgment by 14 votes to two, (Judge Koroma and Judge Adhoc Ajibola dissenting). Awarding Cameroon, the Lake Chad boundary it sought.⁵⁶ The Court also awarded Cameroon the Bakassi Peninsula. The Court obligated both parties to withdraw their police and military from the affected area without any precondition.⁵⁷ In respect Of Equatorial Guinea the Court drew the maritime boundary in the manner it sought.

Post Judgment Compliance: The judgment which was largely in favor of Cameroon initially met with a great deal of reluctance by Nigeria in terms of her unwillingness to comply.

Because the judgment involved giving part of its territory i.e., the Bakassi Local Government Area of Nigeria through its president at the time, General Olusegun Obasanjo argued that the implementation of the judgment would require an amendment of the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (CERN) (1999).⁵⁸

Cameroon contended that both countries previously agreed to fully comply with the ICJ judgment, Nigeria on her part denied the existence of any such agreement.⁵⁹ The government of Nigeria was under intense internal political pressure not to comply with the judgment. There was a corresponding intense pressure by the international community to get Nigeria to comply with the judgment.

Eventually Nigeria began to comply with the ICJ judgment and by January 2006 compliance with the judgment by the 2 States had reached a significant level. In June 2006 the then Secretary General of the United Nations Kofi Annan brokered an agreement towards full compliance with the ICJ judgment by both Nigeria and Cameroon. By the end of 2006 compliance had been largely achieved with the withdrawal of Nigerian troops from the disputed border region.⁶⁰

The ICJ and Problems of Political Influence

Every sovereign state is a political entity, and as such, disagreement between States is political in nature.⁶¹ By comparison, civil cases determined by domestic courts do not have the kind of political high stakes in disputes between Sovereign States who are sometimes prepared to go up in arms against one another. Such matters are always of political significance to the State parties. For example, on November 29, 1979, the United States instituted proceedings against the Islamic Republic of Iran in respect of the seizure, hostage taking and detentions of the United States diplomatic and consular staff in Tehran. The United States

⁵⁵ (2002), FWLR Pt. 132, pg. 1

⁵⁶ Land and Maritime Boundary between Cameroon and Nigeria (Cameroon v. Nigeria; Equatorial Guinea intervening) 97 AJIL (2003) 387

⁵⁷ Land and Maritime Boundary between Cameroon and Nigeria (2002) ICJ Rep. 303, at Para. 325

⁵⁸ Nigeria, Cameroon and the Unending Conflict over Bakassi; Vanguard (Lagos), 27 Feb. 2003

⁵⁹ Ibid

⁶⁰ Cameroon, Nigeria sign agreement decades old border dispute, UN Press Release AFR/1397. 12 June 2006.

⁶¹ Hersch Lauterpacht, *The Function of Law in the International Community* (Oxford: Oxford University Press 1933) 142

contended that the government of Iran had violated international legal obligations for tolerating, encouraging, failing to prevent and punish the hostage taking conduct. In this case, the government of Iran challenged the ICJ's jurisdiction on the ground that the dispute brought by the United States "only represents a marginal and secondary aspect of an overall problem, one such that it cannot be studied separately, and which involves, inter alia, more than 25 years of continental interference by the United States in the internal affairs of Iran."⁶²

Indeed, the origin of the Iran hostage crisis can be traced back to 1951 when Iran's newly elected Prime Minister Muhammed Mossaadeh planned to nationalize Iran's oil industry, which would undoubtedly threaten the strategic interests of the United States over Iran's oil reserves. Anti-American sentiment had already been bubbling beneath the surface when the Shah's government came to power in August 1953. When President Carter allowed the Shah of Iran, Mohammed Reza Pahlavi, to enter the US for the medical treatment of an advanced malignant lymphoma in 1979, long-held anti-American rage in Iran was triggered: a group of pro-Ayatollah students seized sixty-six US diplomats and embassy employees on November 4, 1979.

In the same way, in 1986, the government of Nicaragua brought a claim against the United States in respect of the threat or use of force against Nicaragua and the intervention in Nicaragua's internal affairs. However, this dispute also only forms one element of a broader political dispute between two states during the Nicaraguan revolution. Immediately following the overthrow of the Somoza dictatorship by Sandinistas in 1979, the Regan administration began to allocate both financial and material aids to the Contras, and later secretly and illegally train and arm the Contras in order to destabilize the Sandinista regime.

As one can see from these cases brought to the Court by the member states in the past, the concept of "legal disputes" is a crucial but unfortunately a poorly defined term. On the one hand, it describes the exact scope of Court's judicial function. On the other hand, since all disputes between sovereign states arise in political contexts, how does the ICJ decide whether a question is or is not legal? As Baron Marschall von Bieberstein pointed out at The Hague Peace Conference⁶³ in 1907, "the word *legal* is the nail on which we have hung on it will fail to the ground. Hence, among these contentious cases brought to the ICJ by the Sovereign States, a sharp line between legal and political problems cannot be easily drawn based on the subject-matter or the factual matrix of particular cases.

CONCLUSION

The discussion in this work clearly shows the scope of jurisdiction of the International Court of Justice and the strength or weakness of its compliance record. The work highlights the nature of political influence on the ICJ. A comparison was drawn between how legal scholars see the constrains of the ICJ from a legal point of view focusing more on what could be considered as legal defects especially the compulsory jurisdiction of the court and on the other hand, scholars are of International Relations and some International Law scholars try to see the problem as being largely that of political constrains brought about by the influence of State parties on the activities of the Court.

⁶² Case Concerning United States Diplomatic and Consular Staff in Tehran (*United States of America v Iran*) 1980 ICJ I.

⁶³ Proceedings of The Hague Peace Conference, *Carnegie Endowment for International Peace*, Vol. II, 50